

Promoting policy innovations that promote commons

Insights and recommendations highlighted by ACCTING

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ACCTING's research activities show the positive impact commons can have on a just transition. Commons are inclusive, and their positive impact on marginalised populations is real. Promoting both existing and new commons (i.e., those to be created), is therefore a sensible investment for policymakers who want the transition to be inclusive. This factsheet presents examples of innovative policies that promote and support the commons. Such examples are all too rare today, and the purpose of the factsheet is thus to draw attention to their benefits and to inspire policymakers to support commons. Existing recommendations for policymakers on the importance of commons and the need to support them are also highlighted, with ACCTING research confirming their pertinence and potential for reaching vulnerable and marginalised people.

Recommendations

The aim here is to highlight relevant pre-existing recommendations, from individuals and organisations outside of ACCTING to policymakers who have been active in promoting the commons. The intention is to explore the impact of commons and the need for policy initiatives to support them. This factsheet intends to emphasise that the current neoliberal system often hinders participation in civic life; by perpetuating economic inequalities and social barriers, limiting access to resources, education, and platforms needed for meaningful engagement in decision-making and reform processes. In this section we further accentuate the following recommendations, as the ACCTING research has underlined their relevance and importance. They are relevant for policymakers at various levels, including the local, national and European levels.

Establish laws that officially recognise and support commons governance models alongside public and private models of ownership. This framework should be able to define the rights, responsibilities, and diverse governance mechanisms for communities managing shared resources.

Promote the transformation of unoccupied or underutilised urban spaces into shared green commons through incentives to stimulate the reclamation of these spaces by local communities. At the same time, mandate participatory urban planning processes to involve citizens in the co-creation of green commons.

promoting green commons in unoccupied or underutilised urban spaces

Adopt policies that encourage public–civic partnerships for urban commons, so that grassroots initiatives that aim to create or renew commons can

rely on institutional support when needed and can play a role in urban governance mechanisms to defend their interests. One possible way for (local) policymakers to enable this is to set up funding programmes that support urban commons projects. At the EU level, funding can also be proactively allocated to small-scale community projects (i.e., not carried out by large consortia) through existing programmes like the European Regional Development Fund, the Cohesion Fund, the LIFE programme and the Horizon programme (Bloemen & Hammerstein, 2017). This would have implications for the current design of these programmes: the expanded use of mechanisms like FSTP (Financial Support for Third Parties) could be a way forward to reach small-scale community projects.

 Support energy commons at the EU level by dedicating significant parts of the EU energy budget to community-led renewable energy projects (and the infrastructure that this requires). As highlighted in Hammerstein & Bloemen (2016), EU energy policy can do more to facilitate and promote community-controlled and community-produced renewable energy by having EU funding programmes prioritise commons-based energy production, by enshrining the right to sell electricity to the grid, and by providing financial risk facilities for community energy projects.

 Transition from the EU's current Common Agricultural Policy to a 'Common Food Policy', to de-commodify food and food production and move to a sustainable, community-supported food system. As previously advocated by Vivero-Pol (2019) and IPES Food, a Common Food Policy (CFP) would help harmonise EU policies on food, agriculture, climate, environment, trade, health, and social issues, which are currently – in some cases – working towards contradictory ends. The CFP would enable and support commons-based initiatives like collective food buying groups and community-supported agriculture. These emphasise fairness and environmental sustainability, while reducing the disproportionate influence of large food industry corporations over agriculture and food policy.

Findings from ACCTING

While ACCTING's research did not directly and consistently address questions pertaining to commons, it nevertheless identified the important role commons play in addressing the needs of different target groups (including the most vulnerable) and their potential contribution to a just transition. The concept of commons encompasses both collective resources – including natural resources such as ecosystems, and public resources like energy or public space, and the form of collective ownership, organising and governance (through self-organised and cooperative institutions) of these resources. Findings from across ACCTING's thematic research lines illustrate how commons have played a role in processes of behavioural change towards sustainability.

- In terms of **disaster prevention and recovery**, the management of commons has been shown to play an important role. Whether in cooperation with the (local) authorities or not, communities have come together and used their specialised knowledge to protect and safeguard natural areas in their environment, engaging in disaster prevention, mitigation and recovery efforts when confronted with wildfires, flooding or other similar events. This local caretaking of commons by communities often goes against prevailing neoliberal logics, with authorities ignorant or neglectful of the crucial work performed by residents to counter disasters.
- The impulse to safeguard commons and their **biodiversity** is visible in cases where local communities resist projects that impact their natural surroundings. The research found that biodiversity protection and habitat conservation is emphasised by those living near natural parks or other valued natural areas. Through education and training, these communities aim to ensure that environmentally beneficial practices are promoted and that behaviours are changed, especially among younger generations. Moreover, cultural traditions and practices related to nature were often found to be important in small communities to educate people about how to behave in and with nature. These values and skills support an understanding of the benefits of natural commons and of how to care for them.
- As for **energy consumption and production**, energy community schemes have been highlighted as a form of energy commons with the potential to reduce energy poverty and vulnerability in both urban and rural areas. Motivations to change behaviour and acquire the necessary competences for managing community-owned sustainable energy resources can come from a variety of sources, including the pride that people can feel from participating in energy communities, the need to save on energy costs, and any

financial incentives offered by the authorities (i.e., to install photovoltaic systems). By leveraging these motivations, processes of energy commoning can be stimulated.

- In the case of sustainable food, ACCTING has observed various initiatives and organisations striving to improve the availability of sustainable food and promoting the common-adjacent concepts of edible schools and edible cities. Making food cultivation and preparation more accessible for a multitude of societal groups was a recurring phenomenon for the studied initiatives. By engaging in practices like introducing people to permaculture practices, reusing food waste in cooking activities, and promoting social inclusion through participatory activities, food commons can help promote more sustainable production and consumption behaviours.
- Another area where commoning can motivate behavioural change is in the field of **sustainable mobility**. Mobile commons, where diverse mobility means are shared (as opposed to privately-owned transport means) and co-exist in harmony, promote the shared use of public spaces.

Better Stories

Policy initiatives that promote commons in the context of climate change and the necessary transition are all too rare. In this section, we mention some innovative initiatives from authorities at different levels (from local to EU), that show the way forward.

- Within its energy policy, the EU has long recognised the power of collective, democratic forms of organising the ownership and governance of resources. The 2019, **Clean Energy for All Europeans Package**¹ including the Renewable Energy Directive (REDII) and Internal Energy Market Directive (IEMD), recognises and supports citizen and renewable energy communities as a key contributor to the energy transition. These policies aim to facilitate market access and energy sharing for small-scale, citizen-led renewable energy initiatives. They also require Member States to create an enabling framework to support these communities, for instance in their development of National Energy and Climate Plans. In their transposition into national policies, such as the German Erneuerbare Energien Gesetz (EEG), enabling policies include the legal recognition of energy communities, financial incentives, and special auctioning permissions for small-scale projects to reduce competitive pressures vis-a-vis larger commercial players. While the implementation is still patchy and partly insufficient to foster truly inclusive energy commons, there are today over 9000 energy communities in the EU, involving more than 1.5 million citizens. As such, the EU's energy policy can be regarded as a blueprint to promote commons-based forms of organisation in other Green Deal priority areas, such as food and agriculture, climate action and emerging policy priorities, like housing.
- The **“third place”** is a concept introduced by sociologist Ray Oldenburg (1989) that refers to the space that is neither the home nor the place of work. This is a neutral ground where many social interactions take place. This concept has been interpreted in very diverse ways. France is a country where the concept has been embraced by civil society under the name “tiers-lieu” with a focus on the spatial aspect and social cohesion. The State has developed support mechanisms to strengthen these third places with the creation of hundreds of spaces. This is done through the ANCT (the national agency for “coherence of territories”). An evaluation of this approach is available.

¹ https://wayback.archiveit.org/12090/20241209144917/https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-strategy/clean-energy-all-europeans-package_en

- The **City as a Commons**² project started in 2011 in Bologna with the support from Fondazione del Monte di Bologna e Ravenna and the city of Bologna. This led to new regulation on collaboration between citizens and the city for the care and regeneration of urban commons in the city. This is now known as the Bologna Regulation, a 30-page regulatory framework delineating the ways local authorities, citizens, communities, SMEs, nonprofits and other institutions can co-manage public and private assets. The regulation calls for new frameworks and tools for collaborative urban/local governance. Cities like Ghent and Madrid have tailored the regulation to their circumstances with the aim of establishing a cooperative relationship between the city and its citizens for the management of urban commons.
- The **Tempelhofer Feld**³ is a former airfield of the Tempelhof Airport. It is now used as a park and leisure area, covering around 304 hectares. Since 2010, it has been open to the public for recreational and leisure use, offering various civic projects such as an intercultural education centre, a community garden, a talent school, a high ropes arena, mini art golf, a district garden and more. In a referendum in 2014, the people of Berlin voted against building on the edges of the site and in favour of preserving Tempelhofer Feld in its current state. As a result, the "Law for the Preservation of Tempelhofer Feld" (ThFG) came into force in June 2014, which defines the purpose of the area's protection and the preservation goals. Tempelhofer Feld is a case of success as it is a commons where a referendum was held, and more than 60% of the Berliners supported the idea of banning construction on the former airfield. And the urban garden initiative situated in Tempelhofer Feld reflects the community's use of a common pool of resources. At the same time, a failure as the airfield is now managed in a top-down exclusive manner by the city government.
- Through the **Kleineschholz project**⁴, the City of Freiburg is supporting housing commons in its urban developments. The municipality's bidding process for eleven building permits is open exclusively to common good, oriented actors and follows criteria of affordability, inclusivity and sustainability. It thus excludes profit-driven investors in favour of cooperative and public-led social housing. So far, three housing cooperatives organised under the *Mietshäusersyndikat* (apartment-house syndicate) model have been approved. This model grants a veto right on property sales and privatisation to the Syndikat, thus removing properties from speculative markets to ensure long-term affordability and community-ownership. The resulting self-organised housing projects

² <https://www.shareable.net/how-bologna-is-regenerating-the-urban-commons/>

³ <https://www.tempelhoferfeld.de/en/pflege-entwicklung/about-tempelhofer-feld/>

⁴ <https://kleineschholz-syndikat.org/#mietshaeuser-syndikat>

feature a strong focus on inclusivity, for example, by focusing on mutual care for elderly residents in Birnbaum project and educational space for disadvantaged girls in Elinor-Ostrom Siedlungsprojekt 1 (EOS1). Supported by municipal subsidies tied to rent caps, the Kleineschholz project demonstrates how public-cooperative collaborations can create sustainable housing solutions.

- Amsterdam's **Incubator for the Community Economy**⁵ seeks to support grassroots initiatives and foster a democratic, localised economy. A coalition of civil society organisations, with municipal support, launched the incubator to promote socio-economic change, in line with the vision of the Donut Economy. The incubator supports initiatives that democratise ownership and governance, emphasise social value and ecological regeneration, and create tangible benefits for local communities. Inspired by the principles of commons, the incubator supports diverse models such as cooperatives. Such initiatives often face obstacles like rigid institutional frameworks and funding challenges. The incubator bridges these gaps through funding support, knowledge-sharing, and network-building.

References

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⁵ <https://www.commonsnetwork.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Verkenning-Incubator-Gemeenschapseconomie-Commons-Network-2022.pdf>

About ACCTING

ACCTING is an EU-funded project aiming to understand the impact of Green Deal policies on vulnerable groups, prevent inequalities, and produce knowledge and innovations to advance behavioural change at individual and collective levels.

Running until May 2025 and based on two research cycles, ACCTING mobilises research experimentation and innovation to promote an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal, focusing on the inequalities produced by its policies.

Find out more about the project and discover more factsheets at <https://accting.eu>

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